

Archaeometry Laboratory

University of Missouri

OBJECT LOAN POLICY

The Archaeometry Laboratory at the University of Missouri Research Reactor manages a collection of archaeological and geological material and analytical standards, as defined by its collections management policy ([10.5281/zenodo.14007905](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14007905)). Objects from this collection may be loaned to researchers to further the knowledge of archaeological science. Requests for loan of the material must be made at least one month in advance of the beginning of the requested loan period to the Archaeometry Laboratory via email at archaeometrylab@missouri.edu. Requests should include:

- a) The objects requested for loan;
- b) The proposed duration of the loan;
- c) A project description or purpose for the loan, including any proposed analyses to be undertaken on the loaned objects;
- d) If any of the proposed analyses are destructive, a description of the impact of the proposed sampling or testing;
- e) The locations of facilities where the objects will be stored and any analyses will be undertaken for the duration of the loan;
- f) A list of any individuals who will be responsible for the objects or analyses of the objects during the loan;
- g) A CV of the primary individual requesting the loan, and if the individual is a student, a letter of support from their academic supervisor.

Loans must be consistent with the University of Missouri System's Code of Ethics.

Loans will be made to borrowers affiliated with an academic institution, museum, or other related institution. Objects may not be lent for personal or commercial use. The Archaeometry Laboratory will not loan objects for commercial purposes.

Borrowers will return the loaned object or objects to the Archaeometry Laboratory at the end of the loan agreement, unless otherwise specified.

There are no loan fees associated with loans from the Archaeometry Laboratory. All costs of any analyses are the responsibility of the borrower unless otherwise indicated in the Object Loan Agreement. The borrower assumes responsibility for round trip shipping costs for the objects unless otherwise indicated in the Object Loan Agreement.

Any publications that make use of objects loaned by the Archaeometry Laboratory should acknowledge the Archaeometry Laboratory and its current grant (no. 2208558) from the National

Science Foundation. In some instances, the individuals who contributed the objects to the collection should also be acknowledged, and this information will be provided by the Loan Committee upon approval of the loan.

Data that are the result of any analyses undertaken during the loan are to be provided to the Archaeometry Laboratory at the conclusion of the loan period. These data are subject to the Archaeometry Laboratory's Data Management Policy, available at:
https://archaeometry.missouri.edu/data_management.html.

Loan requests may be submitted to the Archaeometry Laboratory at any time, and will be reviewed by the Laboratory in a timely manner.

Failure to adhere to the guidelines outlined in this policy may result in denial of future loan requests for both the researcher and their institution.

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OBJECT LOAN AGREEMENT FORM

The following object(s) from the collections of the Archaeometry Laboratory at the University of Missouri Research Reactor are provided via loan for analysis:

The purpose of the loan/analytical technique(s) used is:

Dates of Loan: _____

Borrower: _____

Borrower Institutional Affiliation: _____

Borrower E-mail: _____ Borrower Phone: _____

Borrower Address: _____

Borrower Signature: _____ Date: _____

Approval Signature: _____ Date: _____

These object(s) are provided for analysis under the following conditions:

1. No alteration, sampling, modification, or testing of any object is permitted without prior written authorization in the form of a signed Archaeometry Laboratory Loan Agreement. Under no circumstances is testing permitted in the absence of this agreement, including on the basis of verbal discussions with any Archaeometry Laboratory staff member.
2. The objects, usable samples, and any (in the event of destructive testing) unused portions will be returned to the Archaeometry Laboratory at the end of the loan period so that they may be saved for future use. In the event of destructive testing, full documentation regarding the location, extent and kinds of sampling must be maintained and provided to the Archaeometry Laboratory.
3. Any data that are the result of analyses undertaken during this loan are to be provided to the Archaeometry Laboratory at the conclusion of the loan period. These data are subject to the Archaeometry Laboratory's Data Management Policy.
4. The Archaeometry Laboratory and its grant from the National Science Foundation (no. 2208558) will be acknowledged in any publications, presentations, or other public use of data obtained from object(s) included in this loan. Additionally, the following individuals should be acknowledged for their contribution of these objects to the Archaeometry Laboratory's collections:

5. All costs of the analysis, including return shipping, are the responsibility of the researcher, unless otherwise indicated in this agreement.

In addition to this form, please submit a current CV, and if you are a student, a letter of support from your academic supervisor.

Additional notes or conditions:
